

An Analogy Between Clot Burden and Right Ventricular Dysfunction in Acute Pulmonary Thromboembolism on Computed Tomography Pulmonary Angiography Using Modified Millers Score: A One Year Hospital Based Cross Sectional Study

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ABSTRACT

Acute pulmonary thromboembolism (PTE) is a critical cardiovascular condition with high mortality, especially when associated with right ventricular dysfunction (RVD). Computed tomography pulmonary angiography (CTPA) is the standard diagnostic tool for PTE, assessing thrombus burden and RVD indicators. This study aimed to determine the correlation between pulmonary embolism thrombus load, assessed using the Modified Miller Score (MMS), and RVD as demonstrated by CTPA. Additionally, it explored the relationship between thrombus load, CT signs, and 2D echocardiographic features of RVD. A prospective, hospital-based study was conducted over one year at Dr. Prabhakar Kore Hospital and Medical Research Center, Belagavi, involving 49 PTE patients undergoing CTPA and transthoracic echocardiography. CTPA scans were evaluated for PTE severity using MMS and RVD features. A significant association was observed between higher clot burden ($MMS \geq 13$) and RVD markers. Patients with $MMS \geq 13$ exhibited a positive RV/LV ratio in 69.39% ($p = 0.0002$), septal deviation in 30.61% ($p = 0.0012$), and a positive MPA/AA ratio in 65.31% ($p = 0.0025$). RA/RV enlargement was noted in 48.98% ($p < 0.0001$), PASP was elevated in 40.82% ($p < 0.0001$), and TAPSE was significantly lower ($p < 0.0001$). $MMS > 13$ strongly correlated with RVD on CTPA ($p < 0.01$) and may serve as a predictor of RVD, facilitating faster diagnosis of PTE and right heart strain using CTPA alone.

Keywords: PE, PTE, DVT, RV, LV, RVD, CTPA, V/Q, IVC, TAPSE, BNP, NT-proBNP, tPA, USAT, CTEPH, RV/LV, PA/Ao, RV:LV, IVC, PASP, MMS, MRA, SPECT, MDCT, CT-PESI, QS, QOI, RVD/LVD, ECMO

INTRODUCTION

Acute pulmonary thromboembolism (PTE) is a common disease which is potentially fatal and has a high mortality rate. The study was to determine correlation between increasing pulmonary embolism thrombus load and right ventricular (RV) dysfunction as demonstrated by CT pulmonary angiography (CTPA) and to determine the thrombus load threshold which indicates impending RV decomposition. To investigate any relationship between pulmonary thrombus load and 2D Echo features of right ventricular dysfunction. CTPA cannot only diagnose the embolism but also assess other underlying chest conditions that can result in similar clinical symptoms

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Type of study: Prospective analytical observational study

Study duration: January 2024 to December 2024

Ethical committee approval: Obtained

Method of data collection:

- The study is a hospital-based prospective study conducted on 49 patients with PTE who underwent both CTPA (General electronics revolution 128 slice CT scanner) and echocardiography in KLE's Dr Prabhakar Kore Hospital, Belagavi
- The patients underwent CTPA according to the departmental protocol and the scans were the evaluated for the severity of PTE using the modified Miller scoring system and for any

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features of right ventricular decomposition on the CTPA which was correlated with echocardiograph features of right ventricular dysfunction.

Inclusion criteria: All patient ages >18 years undergoing CT pulmonary angiography for suspected PTE.

Exclusion criteria: Suboptimal scans and change of diagnosis

Study variables: Load of pulmonary thromboembolism, short axes of RV/LV and MPA/AA ratio.

Statistical test: Chi-square test, Kolmogorov test, Shapiro-Wilk test, independent test

Modified Millers Score

- ❖ The site of the most proximal thrombus demonstrated gives a score (up to a maximum of 16) indicating the number of involved downstream major segmental arteries.
- ❖ Individual major segmental arteries get scored 1.

- ❖ The minor axes of the RV and LV chambers are taken in axial plane at its widest points and RV:LV ratio is calculated using inner surface of the free wall and the interventricular septum.

- ❖ The presence of septal bowing and maximum main pulmonary artery to ascending aorta diameter are also recorded.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

- Study population comprised of included 49 patients with a mean age of 48.55 ± 16.21 years (range: 25–84 years).

- Correlation between MMS score, mean RV:LV ratio, MPA diameter and AA diameter.

- Association of Right Ventricular Dysfunction Markers with Clot Burden (MMS Categories)

RV/LV	MMS			p-value
	<13	>=13	Total	
Negative	13	2	15	0.0002
	26.53%	4.08%	30.61%	
Positive	10	24	34	0.0012
	20.41%	48.98%	69.39%	
SEPTUM				
Negative	20	11	31	0.0012
	40.82	22.45	63.27	
Positive	3	15	18	0.0025
	6.12	30.61	36.73	
MPA/AA				
Negative	13	4	17	0.0025
	26.53%	8.16%	34.69%	
Positive	10	22	32	0.0025
	20.41%	44.90%	65.31%	

There was significant association between MMS Score and CTPA findings

- Association of Right Ventricular Function Parameters with Clot Burden (MMS Categories)

RA, RV	MMS		Total	p-value
Negative	13	2	15	<.0001
	26.53%	4.08%	30.61%	
Positive	10	24	34	<.0001
	20.41%	48.98%	69.39%	
PASP				
Negative	19	6	25	<.0001
	38.78%	12.24%	51.02%	
Positive	4	20	24	<.0001
	8.16%	40.82%	48.98%	
TAPSE				
Negative	19	5	24	<.0001
	38.78%	10.20%	48.98%	
Positive	4	21	25	<.0001
	8.16%	42.86%	51.02%	

There was significant association between MMS Score and ECHO findings

- In a study conducted by Wongetal, it was concluded that larger thrombusloads (i.e, $MMS \geq 12$) has strongly correlation with RVD, septal shift and increase in pulmonary artery diameter.
- In our study, there was significant correlation between increasing load and RV/LV ratio & MPA/AA ratio and no significant association between increasing thrombus load and septal changes.
- Ourietalconductedaprospectivestudyon150patientsanditwasfoundthatthereliability of CTPAfor PE was excellent for quantifyingthe right-to-left venticularratioandfor the modified Miller for quantifying of pulmonary artery thrombus burden.
- In our study,it was demonstrated that increasing thrombus load beyond 13resulted in increasing RV/LV ratio
- In a study conducted by Mirela et al thrombus load was assessed using a modified Miller score and RVD was associated with increased thrombus load in acute PE and was correlated with both ventricular dimensions & tricuspid annular plane systolic excursion
In our study, in addition to correlation increasing thrombus load to increasing RV/LV ratio, additionally a tipping point of MMS score of 13 beyond which RVD is likely to occur was demonstrated

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